

SYSTEM OF DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES OF FUTURE ENGINEERS IN AN INFORMED EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article focuses on the systematic directions of development of professional competencies of future engineers in the informational educational environment. The role of information communication is important for each growing young generation to fully respond to the demands of the time. In other words, special attention was paid to the special difference in the informational educational environment. Recommendations and instructions for the development of professional competencies of future engineers are given.

In our country, special attention is paid to the training of highly qualified personnel through the organization of the educational process based on the requirements of the times, including the introduction of information and communication technologies in the higher education system. As a result of the reforms of the last five years, the necessary political-legal, socio-economic and scientific-educational foundations for the establishment of New Uzbekistan were created in our country. Based on the in-depth analysis of complex global processes and the results of our country's progress, in the following years, based on the principle of "For human dignity", we will further increase the well-being of our people, transform economic sectors and rapidly develop entrepreneurship, unconditionally ensure human rights and interests, and Development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, developed based on the principle of "From the strategy of actions to the strategy of development" as a result of broad public discussion in order to determine the priority directions of reforms aimed at forming an active civil society In accordance with the state program for the implementation of the "The year of glorification of human dignity and active neighborhood" the following directions occupy the main place in the seven priority areas:

- ensuring spiritual development and bringing the industry to a new level;
- approach universal problems based on national interests;

Based on this, it is not an exaggeration to say that not only educators, but all of us are responsible for the development of each growing young generation into a mature and potential person in all aspects. In order to achieve the result we expect, it would be appropriate if the future teachers and tutors increase and strengthen their knowledge, skills and qualifications, develop them, and do more on their own. The twenty-first century is the age of information technology, which is important for the future and tomorrow of every young

generation. The development of information communications is progressing all over the world. Describe today's situation, one of the urgent issues is the application of information technologies, which are rapidly entering the practice of all fields, into the process of higher education. The global information network can provide information in any field, regardless of capacity and speed, for receiving it in any amount. It cannot be denied that the role and influence of information technology in the development of a well-rounded person, in his independent choice of profession, in professional self-formation, and in the development of professional skills is increasing. Using computers and information technologies, new opportunities are created in the field of education, in educational activities and in the development of students' creative thinking. Information technologies allow to combine education with life in the process of implementation. There will be an opportunity to closely connect education with future professional activity.

Teaching the treasure of science accumulated over the years to today's young future generation, training them to become mature specialists who meet world standards with the help of advanced and modern pedagogical technology and information systems in the world has become one of the main tasks of today's era. One of the important requirements of today is to conduct the educational process using full computer networks.

It is necessary for republican pedagogues to strengthen comprehensive structural reforms in the educational system by mastering advanced pedagogical technologies and applying them to the educational process. For this, it is necessary to teach our pedagogues technological approaches to the educational process, which, in addition to the use of pedagogical technology, will enrich it with the culture, traditions and experience of Uzbekistan.

The professional formation of future engineers begins in the process of professional education at a higher educational institution. The professional formation of future engineers begins in the process of professional education at a higher educational institution. In the curriculum and science programs of technical higher educational institutions, it is envisaged to teach future engineers the secrets of this profession, to provide scientific knowledge, to provide information about the engineering profession, and to create skills.

Seminars, practical and laboratory training in subjects during the educational process allow not only to strengthen theoretical knowledge and turn them into skills, but also to apply them in the practical work process. Such training makes sure that the chosen person has chosen the right profession

Organizing the education system in our country based on the national ideas and requirements of the education of the growing young generation, ensuring that it meets the prospects of society's development and world standards is an urgent issue today.

Fundamentally reforming the education system, cleaning it from the remnants of the past and raising it to the level of developed democratic states, training highly qualified personnel who meet high moral and ethical requirements for the development of society is the common task of the education system employees.

In order to form professional competence in future specialists, first of all, attention should be paid to the development of observability. In order to acquire socio-perceptive competence in the process of pedagogical activity and communication, the specialist must

have humanitarian, social-reflexive, knowledge and skills, a positive professional "I" image, some personal qualities (intellect, will, it is advisable to engage in activities related to the formation of empathy, observation, kindness, emotional tolerance, etc.).

In order to develop the professional competence of future engineers in an informational educational environment, it is necessary to first check their level of ability to use computer technologies effectively and provide them with insights accordingly. The use of visual aids, electronic boards and interesting materials related to the subject will certainly help to achieve the expected result. Certain qualities of a person are formed through a set of practical educational activities. It is necessary for these works to be clearly multi-faceted, and at the same time to carry out mental, physical, moral, aesthetic and labor training based on their integrity. A comprehensive educational approach requires a systematic attitude and management of the educator. Management can be successful only if external and internal factors involved in the educational process and their interaction are taken into account. The knowledge, skills and qualifications of the educator and pedagogue are also important for the development of future engineers into mature specialists. Certain qualities of a person are formed through a set of practical educational activities. It is necessary for these works to be clearly multi-faceted, and at the same time to carry out mental, physical, moral, aesthetic and labor training based on their integrity. The great German pedagogue Adolf Disterverg expressed the following opinion about the pedagogue's constant reading of subjects. "A teacher should regularly study science. Otherwise, it will look like a dead tree and a stone. Just as a dry tree and a stone cannot bear fruit, we cannot expect any results from such teachers in the future." Based on the pedagogical experiences of the countries that are leading the index of the development of information and communication technologies in the world, it is important to widely apply modern information and communication technologies to the educational process and to raise the quality level of education to a new level, to prepare future engineers for professional activities.

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